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INTEGRATING REAL-WORLD SUSTAINABILITY TOPICS INTO ENGLISH

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Abstract. The article considers modern innovative approaches to teaching English in the context of globalization and sustainable development. There is a need for students to develop universal competences related to global thinking, environmental responsibility and ability to interact in a multicultural environment. Practical examples of integration of project and communication approaches in practice are given, including gallery walk format assignments, design discussions and group presentations. The article emphasizes the role of the teacher as a facilitator and demonstrates the importance of incorporating the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into the learning process.

Keywords. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); globalization, innovation, education, communicative approach, critical thinking.

The era of globalization and digitalization has significantly changed the educational space, making foreign language proficiency not just a professional necessity, but also a tool for intercultural interaction and sustainable development. Teaching English today goes beyond traditional language training, integrating cultural, environmental and social aspects. An important direction becomes the orientation of education to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), approved by the UN, which promotes the formation of students' global responsibility and

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critical thinking. According to UNESCO, education for sustainable development aims at developing students' knowledge, skills, values and attitudes necessary to build a just, peaceful and sustainable future. ESD (Education for Sustainable development) implies a shift from the traditional model of transferring knowledge to the formation of an active position of the student, who is ready to analyze, make decisions and act in the interest of society and the planet. In this sense, the teaching of foreign languages is a unique platform for the implementation of sustainable development principles.

Environmental, social and technological challenges of globalization require from the educational system the preparation of individuals who are able to direct themselves in global processes. Teaching English is becoming a key tool for raising students' awareness of global problems and ways to solve them. The integration of SDGs into the educational process contributes to the development of critical and systemic thinking. For example, discussing the topics of sustainable development, ecology, gender equality or social justice in English lessons allows students not only to practice the language but also to broaden their outlook.

Modern methodology of teaching English is based on the communicative, interactive and interdisciplinary principles. Innovative approaches include project-based learning (PBL), use of digital tools, and the organization of collaborative forms of work in groups. Project training promotes the development of self-reliance, responsibility and creative thinking skills. Integrating SDGs into language education requires a comprehensive approach. Teachers can use the following strategies:

1. Thematic planning: building modules related to individual SDGs, such as "Gender Equality" or "Climate Action".

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2. Use of authentic materials: work with news, interviews, UN and UNESCO reports.
4. Intercultural interaction: international online discussions and debates.
5. Competency assessment: not only assessing language skills, but also understanding global topics.

When educators aim to provide classroom tasks that motivate students to explore the wider world and reflect on how events impact their lives, the learning process becomes significant and relevant. English teachers, in many parts of the globe, have led significant changes in education. Communication tasks, collaborative work, learner autonomy, project work, are all grounded in a concept of learning that recognizes students as engaged participants and thinkers, instead of mere passive absorbers of knowledge (Maley and Peachey, 2017).

The future of our planet is in the hands of today's young generation. By developing the awareness and understanding the Global Goals through engaging and creative activities, we believe that students will not only enrich their vocabulary and enhance their English language skills in a meaningful, creative and memorable way but also develop interest, concern, motivation and a sense of social responsibility for major issues facing all people and our planet today. (Maley and Peachey, 2017).

English language classes are considered to be effective when students are involved in active interaction and research activities. For example, the "Gallery walk" technique makes it possible to turn a teaching process into an interactive exhibition. In one of my classes, students worked in groups on the topic "Renewable Energy" (SDG 7, 9). Each group chose a certain type of renewable energy (solar, wind, hydropower, etc.), prepared posters and presentations,

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analyzed the advantages and disadvantages of the selected source, and then convinced others that their choice was the most promising. After all the projects were submitted, a vote was held for the best option - for example, solar panels. This format develops the skills of public speaking, argumentation, critical thinking, and at the same time, students will understand the importance of reliable energy, analyze characteristics of energy and select sources appropriately.

Another example of project work is discussion, for instance the topic "Benefits and potential dangers of the tourist industry" (SDG 8). Students investigate the impact of tourism on the economy and environment, analyze specific examples from different countries, and then present the results in the form of presentations and mini-debates. This activity develops analytical thinking and the ability to express opinions on complex issues.

The project "City of the future" (SDG 11) is also successfully implemented, where students create a concept for the city of the future, discuss issues of ecology, transport connections, architecture and social infrastructure. This project combines language practice with the development of creativity and global vision.

To raise awareness of the problems and consequences of youth unemployment and get students to think about possible solutions "Youth unemployment" (SDG 8) activity will be helpful. Students create some form of presentation to inform other people about the problems and possible solutions to youth unemployment. They could do this in the form of a written report, infographic, video or slide presentation. Students are encouraged to think creatively about the solutions to some of the problems of youth unemployment. During these assignments, learners use English as a tool to search for information, write reports, create presentations and conduct discussions. It helps to raise awareness of the problems and

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consequences of youth unemployment and also learn the vocabulary related to unemployment. (Maley and Peachey, 2017).

“Youth for Climate» (SDG 13) activity aims to raise students’ awareness of energy issues, to encourage climate action and to engage students in preparation of a group presentation or video about the role of young people in solving climate problems allows them to design a better, sustainable future. Researchers (Coyle, Hood & Marsh, 2010; Leicht, Heiss & Byun, 2018) note that such integration increases the motivation of students and contributes to the formation of a meaningful, valuable attitude towards learning.

Experience of introducing elements of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in teaching English to international students has shown that such an approach significantly expands the educational potential of the discipline. Above all, there is an increase in the internal motivation of students, because discussing global issues such as climate change, social inequality, human rights, gender equality - arouses genuine interest among students and promotes personal involvement in the learning process.

For the teacher, the introduction of SDGs opens up new prospects for professional development. This approach requires flexibility, search for relevant materials, use of modern techniques and digital tools. However, it contributes to updating the course content and makes learning more dynamic, interdisciplinary and responsive to contemporary educational challenges.

The integration of innovative methods and sustainable development goals into teaching English opens up new opportunities for students to develop global competencies. Such approaches not only contribute to language development, but also shape a worldview based on the values of cooperation, responsibility and

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sustainable future. Thus, the teaching of English in the university becomes an important tool for implementing the principles of sustainable development and forming a citizen of the world of the 21st century.

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